

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

CATALOGUE OF TRANSFORMATIVE INTERVENTION METHODS FOR VARIOUS ENABLING PLAYERS AND CONTEXTS

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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PLANET4B

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CGE	Culture Goes Europe
CU	Coventry University
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
FIBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
OOF	Oslo og Omland Frilfutsråd – Greater Oslo Council for Outdoor Recreation
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social IEarning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
RU	Radboud University
UNEP-WCMC	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIFI	University of Pisa

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Executive summary

- This report presents a curated catalogue of biodiversity engagement methods designed to support inclusive, reflexive, and transformative biodiversity engagement.
- The catalogue features 18 methods for biodiversity engagement, arranged in thematic categories including storytelling, sensory, game-based, behaviour, dialogue and debriefing methods.
- The featured methods have been trialled within the PLANET4B project, including across a wide range of social-ecological contexts.
- The catalogue is designed to spark curiosity and support initial orientation. It offers clear, accessible overviews of selected methods, encouraging users to explore extended descriptions, resources, and training materials via the *care-full courses and resources* lighthouse platform: care-full-courses.com.
- The catalogue is also available within the *care-full courses and resources platform* as a digital tool with an expanded, searchable method repository.

1 Introduction

The biodiversity crisis represents an existential and wicked challenge, characterised by complex interdependencies, persistent knowledge–action gaps, and entrenched socio-political structures that resist change (IPBES, 2019; IPBES, 2024). Despite growing awareness and policy commitments, responses often fail to disrupt the direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss or to foster meaningful public engagement, resulting in solutions that lack cultural resonance, local ownership, and long-term effectiveness (Davila et al., 2021; Barton et al., 2024). This disconnect is compounded by governance approaches that privilege technocratic expertise over experiential, emotional, and relational forms of knowing (Fischer & Riechers, 2019; Franklin, 2022).

To address these limitations, a core concern of the PLANET4B project has been to explore the potential of three sets of methods to catalyse more inclusive, reflexive, and transformative forms of biodiversity decision-making: creative and arts-based, deliberative, and behavioural methods (including experiential games, framing and heuristics testing). Applied within PLANET4B as forms of research-based intervention, these methods sets have been developed and adapted to act not merely tools for *understanding*, but rather to serve equally as action-oriented forms of *intentional practice* aimed at unsettling dominant paradigms, legitimising diverse knowledge systems, and contributing to systemic change.

Many of the engagement methods explored within PLANET4B have piloted across the project's [11 case studies](#). This provided an opportunity to test the methods across a diverse range of settings – including five place-based and six sectoral – each offering distinct contextual challenges and opportunities. Central to this process was collaboration with a wide array of stakeholders and research participants, whose contributions shaped the adaptation and application of the methods. This deliverable presents a curated *catalogue of transformative engagement methods* drawn from this applied work.

The catalogue is intended for a broad audience of key enabling players (including policymakers, civil society organisations and private sector actors). It is available in two complementary formats: a downloadable PDF version (see Annex) showcasing 18 methods and an expanded online search tool (featuring 50+ methods), hosted on the PLANET4B *Care-full Courses and Resources* digital platform ([Deliverable 5.9](#)). Together, these formats provide a structured entry point and gradual progression into more sustained engagement with the creative and participatory approaches explored across the project's case studies and beyond. This progression supports the inclusive uptake of engagement methods by a full range of actors, in ways that respond to the biodiversity crisis while remaining sensitive to intersectional dynamics and attuned to the plurality of values, attitudes, and norms shaping decision-making.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the methodology underpinning the development of the catalogue, including the selection, adaptation, and validation of methods across PLANET4B's case studies. Section 3 presents an overview of the catalogue itself, organised into five thematic categories, and highlights its conceptual framing and pedagogical orientation. The full PDF version of the catalogue – featuring 18 curated methods – is included in Annex 1, while the Results section serves primarily as a navigational guide to its contents. Section 4 concludes with reflections on the catalogue's intended use and future development.

2 Methodology: Developing the catalogue of biodiversity engagement methods

2.1 Origins, selection and adaptation of methods for inclusion in the downloadable Catalogue

The methodological foundation of the catalogue of transformative methods is derived in Work Packages (WP) 2 and 3 of the PLANET4B project. Whilst WP2 was focused towards the identification, adapting, development and provision of consortium training in the use of the three main methods sets (creative and arts-based, deliberative, and behavioural methods), WP3 co-ordinated the case study based empirical research. Meanwhile, the theoretical foundation for the catalogue was provided by WP1, including especially the review of behavioural theories ([Deliverable 1.2](#), see also [Deliverable 1.7](#)) and the close attention afforded to intersectionality and researcher positionality (see [Deliverable 1.3](#)).

The methods featured within the catalogue predominately originate from the long-list of 100 methods ([Deliverable 2.1](#)), of which a sub-set of 28 methods were then selected for adaptation and testing within the individual case studies ([Deliverable 2.2](#)). The 11 case studies provided a rich and extended opportunity to explore how transdisciplinary research-based intervention can support and advance pro-biodiversity behaviour and decision-making across interpersonal, intrapersonal, and institutional scales. Core to this was a study design which centred the empirical work around the participation of learning communities (within the 5 place-based case studies) and stakeholder advisory boards (within the 6 sector-based case studies) ([Deliverable 3.1](#)). Over a 12–18 month period, these transdisciplinary communities of researchers and expert volunteer participants, contributed to the review and testing of sub-set of 28 methods. The results produced grounded insights into their practical application, contextual relevance and

transformative potential for fostering inclusive and transformative change in real-world settings (see especially, [Deliverable 3.3](#)). The catalogue draws directly from this body of work, ensuring that the methods included are not abstract or idealised, but have been tested in real-world settings and informed by iterative feedback from a diversity of societal groups.

The featured methods reflect a balance between method type (across the three main PLANET4B method sets) and practical applicability, including suitability for different settings and user groups, and consideration of varying budgets, timeframes, and facilitation resources. The final selection was also informed by criteria such as accessibility, adaptability, emotional and cognitive engagement potential, and capacity to act at different leverage points within biodiversity decision-making systems (Soliev et al., 2025; Leventon et al., 2021; [Deliverable 2.2](#)). There is, however, an overall bias towards methods targeting higher leverage points – such as shifting mindsets, worldviews, and underlying paradigms (Meadows, 1999; Abson et al., 2017; Soliev et al., 2025). This emphasis reflects the project's broader commitment to engaging with the complexity of biodiversity decision-making by recognising intersectional experiences, embracing diverse knowledge systems, and attending to the plurality of values and norms that shape human–nature relationships. In doing so, the selected methods contribute to more inclusive and transformative engagement practices capable of challenging dominant paradigms and supporting systemic change.

The catalogue is intended for a diverse range of actors with the potential to advance biodiversity considerations in decision-making, including policy professionals, civil society organisations, business sustainability champions, and researchers. It has been designed to support both newcomers to creative engagement methods and experienced facilitators seeking to expand their methodological repertoire. Produced in two formats – an online search tool featuring an extended database of 50+ methods, and a downloadable version showcasing a curated subset of 18 methods – the catalogue aims to foster curiosity and support ethical and context-sensitive application. It is particularly relevant for those working at the interface of policy, practice, and public engagement, with a desire to contribute to achieving more just and transformative biodiversity outcomes.

2.2 Expanding access: online catalogue and digital search tool

The catalogue has been designed to be informative both as a stand-alone resource and as a complement to the PLANET4B *Care-full Courses and Resources* platform: care-full-courses.com (Deliverable 5.9). In addition to hosting the full digital catalogue of methods (together with interactive search tool filters), the digital platform contains the PLANET4B *Educational Courses*, and a range of additional curated project resources (for a detailed description of the full contents and structure of the platform see [Deliverable 5.9](#)).

The downloadable PDF version of the catalogue thus serves as an entry point to the digital platform. Its graphic design and concise format are intended to spark curiosity and support initial orientation, particularly for users unfamiliar with participatory approaches. In parallel, the method summaries contained within the digital version of the catalogue are cross-referenced with the corresponding educational course modules (each specifically targeted towards a key enabling player), allowing users to move

seamlessly between the catalogue and the online learning environment. This dual-format approach enables learners to preview methods in the catalogue and then access detailed guidance, video content, and contextual examples via the platform. In doing so, the catalogue reinforces the course's emphasis on reflexivity, ethical facilitation, and situated learning.

To further facilitate seamless navigation between the catalogue and the online platform, QR codes and digital access points are embedded throughout the PDF version. They provide direct links to relevant course modules, facilitator resources, and supplementary materials. The use of QR codes enhances accessibility and supports blended learning, allowing users to transition easily from printed or PDF formats to online digital content. This design choice reflects PLANET4B's commitment to inclusive, multimodal learning and ensures that the catalogue functions not only as a static resource but as a dynamic gateway to ongoing engagement. Together, the two versions of the catalogue and wider lighthouse platform form a coherent learning ecosystem that supports both introductory engagement and deeper pedagogical development.

3 Results: Catalogue of biodiversity engagement methods

3.1 Presenting the Catalogue of biodiversity engagement methods

The curated catalogue presented in this deliverable organises biodiversity engagement methods into five thematic categories: Story and Expression; Sensory and Material Engagement; Play and Game-Based Learning; Systems and Behaviour; Dialogue and Reflection. These categories reflect distinct pedagogical orientations and modes of engagement, supporting users in identifying approaches that align with their strategic aims, facilitation capacities, and contextual needs. For instance, storytelling methods foreground narrative and cultural meaning-making; sensory methods engage embodied and affective responses; play-based approaches foster experimentation and imagination; systems methods support structural analysis and strategic thinking; and dialogue methods facilitate deliberation and collective sense-making. This thematic framing enables both targeted selection and cross-category exploration, enhancing the catalogue's utility for diverse actors across policy, civil society, research, and business. The full catalogue, including method profiles, visual design elements, and links to further resources, is provided in Annex 1.

Each method entry includes guidance on pedagogical potential, contextual relevance, and ethical facilitation, enabling users to assess its suitability for specific decision-making settings. In doing so, the catalogue contributes to PLANET4B's broader aims by promoting inclusive, reflexive, and transformative biodiversity governance, and by encouraging uptake of approaches that can intervene meaningfully across multiple leverage points within complex systems (Meadows, 1999; Abson et al., 2017; Soliev et al., 2025).

To support this, the catalogue integrates principles of intersectionality and the ethics of care in its framing and presentation. Methods are contextualised to reflect how social identities – such as race, gender, age, and cultural background – shape experiences of biodiversity and engagement. This ensures that methods are not presented as

universally applicable, but as adaptable tools requiring sensitivity to local power dynamics and lived realities (Mendes & Inoue, 2024; Barton et al., 2024). The ethics of care is reflected in the attention given to emotional safety, relational accountability, and facilitation responsibilities (Moriggi, 2022; Ghafran & Yasmin, 2025), encouraging users to approach biodiversity engagement as a relational and ethical practice rather than a purely technical exercise.

The Reflexivity–Situatenedness Matrix (RSM) developed within PLANET4B ([Deliverable 1.7](#), [Deliverable 2.3](#), see also Soliev et al., 2025) serves as a conceptual anchor for the catalogue, informing both method selection and framing. The RSM prompts users to consider how each method engages with positionality, power, and context, and whether it operates at shallow or deep leverage points within decision-making systems (Soliev et al., 2025). This connection is made explicit through annotations and framing notes that highlight reflexive and situated dimensions, enabling users to critically assess not only what a method does, but how and why it might contribute to transformative change. By embedding the RSM into the catalogue’s structure, PLANET4B ensures that the resource supports thoughtful, context-aware engagement rather than prescriptive or instrumental use.

3.2 Limitations

While the catalogue offers a valuable synthesis of creative biodiversity engagement methods, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the selection of methods reflects those trialled and validated within the scope of the PLANET4B project, meaning that promising approaches beyond the consortium’s reach may not be represented. Second, while the thematic categories – Story and Expression; Sensory and Material Engagement; Play and Game-Based Learning; Systems and Behaviour; Dialogue and Reflection – provide a useful heuristic for navigation, they are not mutually exclusive and may oversimplify the complex, overlapping pedagogical dimensions of each method. Third, although the catalogue is designed to be accessible and visually engaging, its effectiveness in diverse decision-making contexts depends on users’ willingness and capacity to engage critically with the underlying principles of reflexivity, care, and situatedness. Finally, the catalogue’s integration with the Care-full Courses platform relies on digital infrastructure and literacy, which may limit accessibility for some user groups. These limitations underscore the importance of treating the catalogue as a living resource – one that invites adaptation, expansion, and ongoing reflection.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented a curated catalogue of biodiversity engagement methods developed and trialled through the PLANET4B project. Drawing on empirical insights from 11 place-based case studies and wider consortium collaboration, the catalogue offers a practical and ethically grounded resource for key enabling players seeking to support inclusive and transformative biodiversity decision-making.

The catalogue is available in two complementary formats: a downloadable PDF version, which is the primary focus of this report, and an expanded online search tool hosted on the Care-full Courses and Resources platform. Together, these formats

support accessible exploration and uptake of creative methods for engaging with biodiversity-related challenges.

Organised into five thematic categories – Story and Expression; Sensory and Material Engagement; Play and Game-Based Learning; Systems and Behaviour; Dialogue and Reflection – the catalogue provides a structured yet flexible entry point for users working across policy, civil society, research, and business. These categories are intended as navigational aids rather than rigid classifications, recognising that many methods operate across multiple dimensions and require context-sensitive application.

Importantly, the catalogue is not a prescriptive toolkit. It is designed to support behaviour change through inclusive engagement – encouraging users to reflect on how methods are facilitated, adapted, and embedded within their own decision-making environments. Its integration with the Care-full Courses platform enables users to move from initial exploration to deeper engagement, while QR codes embedded throughout the PDF enhance accessibility and blended learning.

Looking ahead, the catalogue will be disseminated through PLANET4B's stakeholder networks, policy dialogues, and educational outreach activities. Future iterations may incorporate additional methods, case study insights, and user feedback, ensuring the resource remains responsive to evolving needs and challenges in biodiversity governance.

In closing, the catalogue affirms the importance of creative, inclusive, and care-informed engagement in shaping more just and ecologically attuned futures. It supports transformation not only in what decisions are made, but in how they are made, and by whom.

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Statement on data availability

Information relating to the development, adaptable and testing of individual methods during the case study research is available via the [PLANET4B](#) website and via [Zenodo](#) (see, in particular, Deliverables [2.1](#), [2.2](#), [2.3](#), [3.1](#), [3.2](#), [3.3](#)).

Training materials on engagement methods and also a digital version of the Catalogue (containing the full list of PLANET4B ‘Spotlight’ and ‘Snapshot’ methods) are available at care-full-courses.com.

Statement on ethics

Ethical approval was granted for all research undertaken within WP2 of PLANET4B by Coventry University on 17.06.23 – ethical approval project reference number: P160041.

The material contains in the Catalogue and this associated deliverable report is limited to secondary analysis and synthesis of the full versions of the methods included in [Deliverable 5.9](#) (‘Online training and educational resources for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change’) and an accompanying review of relevant academic and grey literature.

Annex

Catalogue of Biodiversity Engagement Methods

PLANET4B

Foreword

Have you ever wondered how to engage colleagues, family members, your local community, or pupils in thinking differently about nature? Or how to spark more meaningful action for biodiversity through your projects, campaigns, or policies? Then this Catalogue of Methods is for you.

Biodiversity – the variety of life on Earth – is disappearing at an alarming rate. This loss affects not only ecosystems but also the health, wellbeing, and resilience of societies. Reversing this trend requires more than technical fixes; it calls for transformative change – a deep shift in how we think, act, and organise our societies.

This catalogue is one of several outputs that reflect the collaborative, transdisciplinary ethos of the PLANET4B project. It showcases a curated set of methods specifically adapted to enhance nature–society relations and support pro–biodiversity decision–making.

The methods are designed not only to inform but to provoke reflection, dialogue, and action across sectors and communities. Within PLANET4B they have been used to engage people in ways that are inclusive, context–sensitive, and transformative.

We hope you will find in this catalogue both inspiration and practical tools to foster meaningful change in how biodiversity is understood, valued, and acted upon in a diversity of settings within education, business, policy and society at large.

The PLANET4B Coordination Team

Catalogue of Biodiversity Engagement Methods

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About PLANET4B

Biodiversity – the variety of life on Earth – is disappearing faster than ever before. Forests, wetlands, and coral reefs are being lost; species are vanishing; and the ecosystems that provide us with food, clean air, water, and climate regulation are under growing pressure. In short, biodiversity forms the very foundation of human wellbeing – yet, despite decades of warnings, meaningful action has often fallen short.

Accordingly, the PLANET4B project (understanding *Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, Behaviour and social learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision-making*) asked two simple but profound questions:

Why do we know so much about the crisis, yet act so little to stop it?

and **how** can we change that?

To find some answers to these questions, we looked at how our **values, social expectations, everyday habits, and ways of learning** influence the choices we make that affect biodiversity. In simple terms, what we care about, what feels normal, how we behave, and what we were taught all shape how we treat the natural world.

Through a series of eleven case studies (ranging from school gardens impacts on pupils through integrating disabled children to nature to enabling migrant youth in experiencing nature) bringing together academic researchers, charitable and private sector practitioner organisations, educators and community partners across Europe, we co-created methods that help prioritise biodiversity while supporting inclusive change at individual, community, and political levels.

Why This Catalogue?

This catalogue showcases a selection of methods adapted and used within one or more of PLANET4B's eleven case studies. Each method has been chosen for its potential to support biodiversity-related transformation through inclusive, creative, and context-sensitive engagement. The aim is to provide an easy-to-use overview of a range of different methods, for practitioners, educators, policymakers and community leaders seeking inspiration or guidance. While the catalogue offers concise introductory summaries, more detailed accounts – including implementation guides, case study examples, and facilitation tips – can be accessed via the [Care-Full Courses and Resources platform](#).

Who this Catalogue is for:

The catalogue is intended for a wide range of audiences, including:

- **Civil society and community organisers** – who may wish to use it to plan inclusive engagement activities or adapt methods to local contexts.
- **Educators and facilitators** – who may want to draw on it to support experiential learning, storytelling, or creative reflection.
- **Policymakers and institutional actors** – who may find inspiration for participatory processes, behavioural interventions, or citizen science initiatives.
- **Businesses and sustainability teams** – who may like to use the methods to support biodiversity awareness, employee engagement, and environmental-social-governance related initiatives.
- **Researchers** – who can draw upon the different featured methods as forms of research-based intervention to better understand and support transformation at intrapersonal, interpersonal, and institutional levels.

Whether you are designing a workshop, planning a campaign, embedding biodiversity into workplace culture, or exploring new ways to connect people with nature, this catalogue – in combination with the [Care-Full Courses and Resources platform](#) – offers a starting point for action, learning, and change.

Thematic Overview: Method Types & Themes

The methods in this catalogue are grouped into five thematic categories, each offering a distinct approach to engaging with biodiversity-positive transformation. These categories reflect the diverse ways people connect with nature, make decisions, and co-create change. Many methods combine elements across categories, and their transformative potential is shaped by context, facilitation, and participant agency.

Storytelling and Expression

Methods that centre personal and collective narratives, creative expression and cultural voice. These approaches elevate lived experience and support emotional and political engagement with biodiversity.

Sensory and Material Engagement

Methods that involve tactile, culinary, spatial, or embodied interaction with biodiversity-related themes. These approaches foster mindfulness, curiosity and ecological awareness through direct experience.

Play and Game-Based Learning

Methods that use structured play, challenge or simulation to explore biodiversity concepts and systems. These approaches support experiential learning, systems thinking and collaborative problem-solving.

Behavioural and Choice Architecture

Methods that subtly influence decision-making by shaping environments, defaults and social norms. These approaches include nudging, mapping, and citizen science and can be particularly effective for institutional and policy-level change.

Dialogue and Reflection

Methods that facilitate structured conversation, critical thinking and collective sense-making. These approaches support trust-building, plural knowledges and inclusive deliberation.

A framework (called the Reflexivity-Situatedness Matrix (RSM)), described toward the end of the catalogue, helps readers see how the different methods create change within individuals, among people, and within institutions – and how these approaches can be combined to make a stronger impact.

Intersectional Considerations

Biodiversity loss is deeply entangled with social inequalities. Who has access to nature, whose knowledge is valued and who participates in decision-making are all shaped by intersecting factors such as gender, ethnicity, age, disability, migration, religion and socio-economic status. This catalogue reflects a commitment to **inclusive** practice by showcasing methods that surface underrepresented voices, challenge exclusionary norms, and support plural knowledges.

Many of the methods featured within this catalogue have been specifically adapted during PLANET4B to reflect the lived experiences of groups whose perspectives are often under-represented, including children with disabilities, ethnic minority groups, urban youth and faith-based communities. Facilitators who choose to use the methods are encouraged to reflect on their own positionality, build trust with participants, and co-create safe spaces for dialogue and expression. Intersectionality is not just a lens for analysis – it is a practical approach to designing biodiversity engagement that is socially just, culturally relevant and responsive to diverse needs.

Ethics of Care

Every method in this catalogue is only as good as the approach taken to deliver it. Care-full research practice means thinking not just about what we do, but how we do it – with attention to safety, respect, and inclusion. Whether you're facilitating a photo interview, running a biodiversity game, or hosting a community mapping session, it's important to create spaces where people feel valued, heard, and protected.

This includes practical considerations: ensuring venues are safe and accessible, avoiding emotionally difficult settings, and being mindful of how people are represented. For example, some participants may not feel comfortable sharing personal stories or being photographed – these choices must always be respected. Facilitators should offer clear information about how contributions will be used, and participants should be free to opt out at any time.

If you're collecting data, ethical approval may be needed, and you should use consent forms and participant information sheets. But ethics is not just about forms – it is about trust, transparency, and care. The *Care-Full Courses and Resources* platform was created to support this kind of thoughtful, relational practice. We encourage all users of this catalogue to approach each method with curiosity, humility, and a commitment to care.

Participatory Filmmaking

Storytelling and Expression

Purpose

To empower participants to tell their own stories through film, fostering reflection, dialogue and advocacy around biodiversity-related issues. This method supports inclusive representation, skill-building and transformative engagement by placing creative control in the hands of those most affected.

Key Features

Participants:

- 5-15 people per group
- Ideally drawn from communities or groups with lived experience or a stake in the issue

Estimated Timeframe:

- Minimum: 3 sessions over 2-4 weeks
- Longer timeframes allow deeper engagement and impact

Budget Level:

- Medium to High
- Costs may include equipment, editing, space hire, travel and dissemination

Materials Needed:

- Cameras or smartphones
- Editing software and suitable editing space
- Storage devices (e.g. USBs, SD cards)
- Flipcharts, sticky notes, markers
- Worksheets (filming techniques, ethics)
- Resources for screening (e.g. projector, venue, QR codes)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and inclusive communication
- Project coordination and ethical oversight
- Storyboard script writing and/ or visualisation
- Technical filmmaking (filming, editing, sound)
- Outreach and marketing
- Adaptability and ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in multiple PLANET4B case studies to support inclusive storytelling and biodiversity engagement. For example, in the Brazil (Trade & Global Value Chains) case study, Indigenous youth used participatory Filmmaking to document a protest for education rights, amplifying their voices and connecting local struggles to broader biodiversity and justice concerns.

How It Worked:

Participants were trained in basic filmmaking and ethics, then supported to film their own stories. Facilitators provided guidance while stepping back to allow creative autonomy. Films were collaboratively reviewed and edited with participants shaping narrative, style and dissemination strategies.

Engagement & Participation:

The method fostered deep engagement through co-creation, reflection and shared decision-making. Participants shaped the direction, filmed each other and decided how their stories were told and shared. Safe spaces and ethical dialogue were central throughout.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Strengthened confidence and creative agency of participants
- Fostered new relationships and collective action
- Raised visibility of marginalised perspectives
- Encouraged emotional and political engagement with biodiversity

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Highly adaptable across contexts and communities
- Supports deep reflection and storytelling
- Builds skills and confidence
- Can catalyse personal, collective, and policy change
- Offers rich material for advocacy and education

Considerations:

- Requires significant time, resources, and ethical care
- Participants need support with technical and emotional aspects
- Consent and representation must be revisited throughout
- Safety and privacy must be carefully managed
- Facilitators must balance support with creative autonomy

Participatory Theatre

Storytelling and Expression

Purpose

To explore complex social and ecological issues through interactive performance, enabling participants to reflect on values, emotions, and decision-making. This method fosters empathy, critical thinking and collective imagination – making it especially powerful for engaging with biodiversity, justice and systemic change.

Key Features

Participants:

- Recommended group size: 20–35
- Suitable for school groups, Learning Communities, or community organisations
- Works best when participants have some familiarity with one another

Estimated Timeframe:

- Single session: ~3 hours (including warm-up, performance, and debrief)
- Extended formats: multi-session co-creation over weeks/months

Budget Level:

- Medium to High
- Costs may include facilitator or theatre group fees, venue hire, props, refreshments, and travel

Materials Needed:

- Large room with space for movement
- Basic props, scenery, and costumes
- Refreshments
- Transport support for participants and facilitators
- Optional: audio-visual equipment for documentation
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and emotional sensitivity
- Drama-based methods (role-play, improvisation)
- Project coordination and logistics
- Adaptability and ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B education case study in Hungary with secondary school students. The play *Blindspot*, developed by Káva Theatre Group and WWF Hungary, explored the commodification of a healing plant and its ecological and social consequences. Students stepped into roles within a fictional company, navigating tensions between economic growth and biodiversity loss.

How It Worked:

Actors introduced a scenario, then invited participants to intervene, take on roles and shape the narrative. Participants debated dilemmas, improvised responses, and explored alternative futures. The session concluded with a reflective dialogue linking the performance to real-world contexts.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged through acting, directing, and discussion. The method allowed for varied levels of involvement, including observation. Facilitators ensured emotional safety and inclusivity, with space for multiple viewpoints and creative expression.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Deepened understanding of biodiversity-related trade-offs
- Fostered emotional literacy and moral reasoning
- Strengthened group cohesion and empathy
- Sparked dialogue on systemic change and personal agency
- Enabled creative exploration of alternative futures

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Highly engaging and emotionally resonant
- Supports critical thinking and collaborative learning
- Adaptable to diverse groups and themes
- Encourages embodied and experiential understanding
- Can catalyse dialogue, reflection and action

Considerations:

- Requires skilled facilitation and ethical care
- Not all participants may feel comfortable performing
- Emotional intensity may arise; support must be available
- Preparation and co-creation can be time-intensive
- Budget and logistics need careful planning
- Facilitators must balance support with creative autonomy

Biodiversity Storytelling

Storytelling and Expression

Purpose

To connect personal narratives with ecological and biodiversity-related themes, using storytelling as a tool for reflection, trust-building, and collective learning. This method makes abstract concepts tangible by grounding them in everyday experiences, particularly through food, memory and cultural identity.

Key Features

Participants:

- Ideal group size: 6–8 storytellers
- Plenary discussion can include up to 15 participants
- Suitable for age 11+, adaptable across cultures and contexts

Estimated Timeframe:

- ~2 weeks' notice for storytellers to prepare
- ~2–3 hours facilitator prep (e.g. factsheets)
- 2-hour workshop, optionally followed by a shared meal

Budget Level:

- Low
- Main costs: facilitator time, refreshments, venue, transport support

Materials Needed:

- Factsheets or information cards on selected fruits/vegetables
- Comfortable indoor or outdoor space (weather permitting)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Optional: food samples, illustrated resources, feedback tools

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and inclusive communication
- Workshop planning and recruitment
- Research and preparation of ecological/cultural facts
- Sensitivity to emotional and cultural dynamics
- Adaptability and ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Austrian case study with a Learning Community of migrant women co-creating a biodiverse urban garden. Participants shared stories about meaningful fruits or vegetables, linking personal memories to biodiversity. The session concluded with a communal meal featuring the foods discussed.

How It Worked:

Storytellers prepared personal narratives in advance. During the workshop, stories were shared in small groups, followed by a plenary discussion. Facilitators introduced factsheets to connect stories to nature and culture. The session ended with a shared meal, reinforcing themes of connection and care.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged through storytelling, listening and reflection. Facilitators created a safe, inclusive space with co-negotiated group rules. The method encouraged emotional expression, cultural exchange, and mutual respect.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Strengthened trust and group cohesion
- Elevated experiential and cultural knowledge
- Fostered emotional connection to biodiversity
- Inspired follow-up learning and community action
- Reframed who is seen as a knowledge-holder

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and low-cost
- Builds trust and empathy
- Connects biodiversity to everyday life
- Validates diverse forms of knowledge
- Adaptable to many formats and audiences

Considerations:

- Sensitive topics may arise (e.g. food insecurity, migration)
- Requires careful facilitation and ethical clarity
- Some participants may prefer non-verbal storytelling formats
- Preparation time needed for factsheets and recruitment
- Group dynamics and emotional safety must be actively supported

Photovoice

Storytelling and Expression

Purpose

To enable individuals and communities to document and reflect on their lived experiences through photography, fostering dialogue, critical awareness and advocacy. In biodiversity contexts, Photovoice helps make issues visible and actionable – encouraging ecological relationships and emotional responses, will exposing structural inequalities.

Key Features

Participants:

- Group size: 10–35
- Can be adapted for individuals or smaller groups
- Suitable for new or existing communities; introductory sessions recommended

Estimated Timeframe:

- Minimum: 2 sessions
- Photo-taking period: ~2 weeks (flexible)
- Optional: training workshops and exhibitions

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include equipment, printing, venue hire, refreshments, and facilitator time

Materials Needed:

- Cameras or smartphones
- Flipcharts, sticky notes, markers
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Display materials (e.g. clip frames, foam boards, digital screens)
- Optional: journals, audio recorders, exhibition space

Skills Required:

- Facilitation and inclusive communication
- Project coordination and logistics
- Adaptability and ethical awareness
- Storytelling and caption development
- Strategic planning for dissemination and impact

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B UK case study as part of participatory filmmaking with a Learning Community exploring nature–society relations among Black, Asian and ethnic minority communities. A variant (photo interview) was used in the Swiss case study on organic farming and religion.

How It Worked:

Participants responded to a shared question through photography. They reflected on their images, developed captions and shared stories in facilitated discussions. Selected photos were exhibited with accompanying narratives, sparking dialogue and advocacy.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants had ownership over the process, with flexible timing and modes of engagement. Facilitators supported reflection and storytelling while ensuring ethical care. Peer support and journaling deepened the experience.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Elevated personal and community perspectives
- Fostered emotional connection to biodiversity
- Strengthened group cohesion and trust
- Enabled advocacy through visual storytelling
- Influenced public and policy audiences

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and adaptable
- Encourages creative and critical reflection
- Builds confidence and agency
- Supports inclusive dialogue and advocacy
- Can be used for exhibitions, campaigns and policy engagement

Considerations:

- Requires ethical sensitivity around consent and representation
- Emotional topics may arise; support must be available
- Preparation and facilitation time needed
- Impact depends on thoughtful dissemination and follow-up
- Not all participants may be confident with photography; training helps

Community Mapping

Storytelling and Expression

Purpose

To enable participants to share knowledge, experiences, and visions for a specific place, identifying ecological, cultural and social features. This method supports inclusive planning, strengthens local voices, and can catalyse transformation of public or green spaces, particularly in biodiversity and justice contexts.

Key Features

Participants:

- Recommended group size: 8–50
- Suitable for age 12+
- Works well with existing groups or learning communities; introductory sessions recommended for new groups

Estimated Timeframe:

- ~2 sessions of ~2 hours
- Can be condensed (e.g. [Dotmocracy](#) - voting on ideas with sticky dots: 10–15 mins) or extended over weeks

Budget Level:

- Medium to High
- Mapping itself is low-cost, but follow-up actions (e.g. planning, campaigning, implementation) may require significant resources

Materials Needed:

- Large, printed base maps (e.g. Google Maps, OpenStreetMap, or hand-drawn)
- Visual tools: markers, stickers, photos, magazines
- Comfortable, accessible space (indoor or outdoor)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Refreshments
- Optional: digital mapping tools, 3D models, sensory materials

Skills Required:

- Facilitation and emotional sensitivity
- Project management and logistics
- Technical mapping or design skills (optional)
- Advocacy and campaign planning
- Ability to support inclusive, reflective dialogue
- Adaptability and ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Austrian case study with a Learning Community of migrant women. The group mapped an unused plot near their community garden, developed a plan, and successfully negotiated with the city council to transform it into an edible, biodiverse green space.

How It Worked:

Participants worked in small groups to annotate maps with ecological, cultural and social insights. They identified priorities, barriers and opportunities for transformation. The process was supported by facilitators and followed by further planning and action.

Engagement & Participation:

The method encouraged collaborative visioning, storytelling and spatial reflection. Participants contributed through drawing, discussion, and mapping exercises. Facilitators ensured inclusivity, supported emotional responses and helped translate ideas into action.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Strengthened community identity and agency
- Created a shared vision for space transformation
- Enabled dialogue with local authorities
- Highlighted biodiversity priorities and social needs
- Fostered long-term stewardship and advocacy

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Visually engaging and inclusive
- Builds collective knowledge and action
- Adaptable to diverse contexts and goals
- Supports spatial justice and ecological awareness
- Can influence planning and policy

Considerations:

- Requires careful facilitation of group dynamics
- Emotional or contested topics may arise
- Follow-up support is essential for impact
- Mapping alone may not lead to change without resources or partnerships
- Accessibility and familiarity with maps must be considered

Biodiversity Photo Contest

Storytelling and Expression

Purpose

To engage individuals and communities in documenting biodiversity through photography, fostering awareness, creativity, and advocacy. This method celebrates diverse relationships with nature and can generate powerful visual material for exhibitions, campaigns and community-building.

Key Features

Participants:

- Open to all: hobbyists, gardeners, students, conservationists
- Suitable for individuals or groups; inclusive of children and non-verbal participants
- Can be run locally or online

Estimated Timeframe:

- Flexible: from a few hours to several months (e.g. in PLANET4B the photo contest ran for 3 months)
- Additional time needed for judging and exhibition planning

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include prizes, promotion, exhibition materials, and facilitator time

Materials Needed:

- Camera or smartphone
- Submission platform (online or physical)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Clear judging criteria and anonymised entry system
- Optional: prizes (e.g. seed kits, vouchers), exhibition space, tools library

Skills Required:

- Project coordination and promotion
- Ethical oversight and accessibility planning
- Photography and storytelling support
- Judging and exhibition curation
- Community engagement and outreach

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Hungarian case study to highlight agrobiodiversity. Participants submitted photos across five categories, showcasing gardens, seeds and farming practices. Winners received seed-related prizes and the contest helped build visibility and community around biodiversity.

How It Worked:

Organisers defined themes, promoted the contest, and managed submissions. Judges selected winners based on creativity, relevance and storytelling. Photos were displayed online and in exhibitions, sparking dialogue and further engagement.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants reflected on their relationship with nature through photography. The method supported multilingual and non-verbal expression, making it accessible and inclusive. Public voting and exhibitions extended participation beyond contributors.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Increased awareness and appreciation of biodiversity
- Strengthened local identity and pride
- Fostered community connections and knowledge exchange
- Generated visual content for advocacy and education
- Inspired follow-up initiatives and storytelling

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and engaging for all skill levels
- Encourages creative expression and reflection
- Builds community and visibility around biodiversity
- Flexible and scalable across contexts
- Can be adapted to include storytelling or audio elements

Considerations:

- Requires clear ethical guidance on safety and consent
- Judging must avoid bias toward high-tech equipment
- Impact depends on thoughtful dissemination and follow-up
- Accessibility and inclusion must be actively supported
- Not all participants may be confident with photography; training helps

Biodiversity in the Cupboard

Sensory and Material Engagement

Purpose

To help participants reflect on how everyday food choices impact biodiversity – both locally and globally – and to foster awareness of the connections between consumption, production and ecological systems

Key Features

Participants:

- 4–10 people per group

Estimated Timeframe:

- 2 hours facilitator prep
- 1 week participant prep
- 45-minute session minimum

Budget Level:

- Low

Materials Needed:

- Camera phones and WhatsApp or method to share photos (e.g. an email address)
- Large world map (A1/A0)
- Map pins with flags
- Ingredient lists and global production data
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Refreshments

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and inclusive communication
- Research and preparation of food data
- Workshop promotion and participant recruitment
- Adaptability and ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the UK PLANET4B case study with a Learning Community connected to Dadima's CIC, an intergenerational collective supporting inclusive access to nature for Black, Asian, and ethnic minority communities.

How It Worked:

Participants submitted photos of food items from their cupboards, including ingredient lists and country of origin. These were mapped onto a large world map using pins. Facilitators guided discussions around biodiversity impacts, farming systems and cultural significance.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged in mapping, discussion, and reflection. Facilitators created a safe, non-judgmental space, acknowledging sensitivities around food insecurity, cultural traditions and climate anxiety.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Raised awareness of biodiversity impacts of food systems
- Encouraged critical thinking and curiosity, made space for nuanced discussion
- Fostered reflection on personal and collective food choices
- Highlighted cultural and ecological connections to food

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and low-cost
- Encourages embodied and visual learning
- Adaptable to diverse groups and settings

Considerations:

- Requires careful facilitation around sensitive topics
- Dependent on participant willingness to share personal food habits
- Preparation time needed for research and materials

Drawing in Nature Workshop

Sensory and Material Engagement

Purpose

To foster observation, reflection, and connection with biodiversity through creative engagement. This method encourages participants to slow-down, notice overlooked details and explore their relationship with nature through drawing – regardless of artistic skill. It supports mindfulness, emotional expression, and ecological awareness.

Key Features

Participants:

- Ideal group size: 4–12
- Suitable for age 12+
- Can be adapted for silent reflection or verbal discussion

Estimated Timeframe:

- Typically 2–3 hours
- Can be extended across multiple sessions or integrated into events

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include art materials, facilitator time, venue hire and accessibility support

Materials Needed:

- Outdoor or indoor nature-rich location
- Seating and workspace (tables, boards, clipboards)
- Weather protection (gazebos, umbrellas)
- Art supplies: pencils, pens, paints, paper
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Optional: natural materials for eco-printing or rubbings

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and inclusive communication
- Basic familiarity with drawing techniques
- Emotional sensitivity and adaptability
- Workshop planning and logistics
- Adaptability and ethical awareness
- Optional: artistic or ecological expertise

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Hungarian case study on agrobiodiversity. Participants explored a farm, selected natural elements to draw, and engaged in reflective dialogue. The method was also used during a project partner gathering to slow the pace and deepen reflection.

How It Worked:

Participants began by drawing something they liked, then repeated short drawing exercises with varied prompts (e.g. something overlooked, decaying, or shaped by humans). Sharing and discussion followed each round, with options for quiet reflection. The workshop closed with a group dialogue on insights and emotional responses.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged through observation, drawing, and storytelling. The method supported diverse forms of expression and could be adapted for different comfort levels. Facilitators guided reflection and created a safe, non-judgmental space.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Heightened sensory awareness and mindfulness
- Emotional connection to biodiversity
- Strengthened group cohesion and communication
- Inspired sustainable behaviours and ecological curiosity
- Provided a creative, inclusive entry point into environmental dialogue

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible to all skill levels
- Supports emotional and sensory engagement
- Encourages reflection and ecological awareness
- Adaptable to diverse settings and themes
- Can complement scientific or policy work with creative insight

Considerations:

- Requires thoughtful facilitation and emotional care
- Weather and accessibility must be planned for
- Some participants may prefer alternative formats
- Impact depends on follow-up and integration into wider engagement
- Consent and ethical clarity needed if used for research

Vegetable Exhibition

Sensory and Material Engagement

Purpose

To celebrate agrobiodiversity and engage communities in sustainable food systems through interactive exhibitions. This method showcases heritage and diverse vegetable varieties, fosters dialogue between growers and the public, and raises awareness of biodiversity, seed sovereignty and climate-resilient agriculture.

Key Features

Participants:

- Growers, chefs, researchers, community members and the general public
- Suitable for all ages; inclusive of multilingual and culturally diverse audiences

Estimated Timeframe:

- Planning begins at the start of the growing season
- Exhibition duration: 1 day to several days
- Can be standalone or part of a larger event

Budget Level:

- Medium to High
- Costs may include venue hire, materials, transport, promotion, refreshments, insurance and accessibility support

Materials Needed:

- Tables, chairs, display boards, signage
- Tasting stations, utensils, compostable materials
- Ways to convey further information (e.g. QR codes, flyers, multilingual materials)
- Interactive games, art supplies, feedback tools
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)

Skills Required:

- Event planning and logistics
- Community engagement and facilitation
- Promotion and partnership building
- Accessibility and inclusion planning
- Adaptability and ethical awareness
- Optional: culinary, agricultural, or artistic expertise

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Hungarian case study around agrobiodiversity to showcase heirloom and exotic vegetable varieties. Growers offered tastings and shared stories, creating a vibrant space for learning, exchange and celebration of agrobiodiversity.

How It Worked:

Organisers coordinated with growers, planned the layout, and facilitated interactive activities. Visitors engaged through tasting, games, storytelling and discussion. The event created opportunities for education, networking and advocacy.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants contributed through growing, exhibiting, storytelling, and attending. The method supported inclusive participation through multilingual materials, cultural programming, and sensory engagement. Activities like recipe challenges and collaborative art deepened involvement.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Raised awareness of agrobiodiversity and sustainable agriculture
- Strengthened local food networks and grower collaboration
- Fostered cultural exchange and culinary storytelling
- Inspired behavioural shifts in food choices and growing practices
- Created momentum for ongoing engagement and advocacy

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Visually and sensorially engaging
- Builds community and cross-sector collaboration
- Supports education, advocacy and cultural celebration
- Adaptable to different scales and settings
- Can be embedded in broader biodiversity strategies

Considerations:

- Requires significant planning and budget
- Accessibility and inclusion must be actively supported
- Impact depends on follow-up and integration into wider efforts
- Ethical and safety guidance needed for tastings and storytelling
- Weather and venue logistics must be carefully managed

Biodiversity Cookbook

Sensory and Material Engagement

Purpose

To preserve and promote agrobiodiversity by collecting and sharing traditional, seasonal and underutilised recipes. This method fosters intergenerational dialogue, cultural reflection and ecological awareness, linking food practices to biodiversity conservation and seed sovereignty.

Key Features

Participants:

- Suitable for age 14+
- Can involve students, families, growers, chefs and community members
- Works well in schools, community groups, or place-based research settings

Estimated Timeframe:

- Flexible: from a few weeks to a full growing season
- Includes time for recipe collection, cooking, documentation and publication

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include printing, digital design, photography, cooking ingredients and event hosting

Materials Needed:

- Camera or smartphone
- Kitchen and/or garden access
- Art supplies or digital tools for cookbook design
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Reference sources for plant history and cultivation tips

Skills Required:

- Facilitation and community engagement
- Recipe writing and editing
- Cultural sensitivity and ethical care
- Project coordination and digital publishing
- Optional: gardening, cooking or storytelling expertise

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Hungarian education case study to create a vegetarian cookbook featuring underutilised vegetables suited to the local climate. Recipes were accompanied by cultivation tips and cultural insights. The cookbook was published online as a free gift in [Hungarian](#) and [English](#) by the Magház Community Seed Association.

How It Worked:

Participants (authors and contributors) selected vegetables, researched their origins, developed recipes and documented the process through photography. Recipes were compiled into a digital cookbook, with potential for translation, distribution and integration into educational or community settings.

Engagement & Participation:

The method encouraged intergenerational interviews, storytelling, and cultural exchange. Contributors reflected on food memories, biodiversity, and seasonal eating. The cookbook served as both a creative output and a tool for advocacy and education.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Raised awareness of agrobiodiversity and seed systems
- Preserved cultural food knowledge
- Inspired sustainable eating and growing practices
- Strengthened community identity and intergenerational dialogue
- Prompted requests for heritage seeds and further engagement

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and adaptable across contexts
- Combines creativity, research, and advocacy
- Supports cultural and ecological literacy
- Can be used for fundraising, education, or community building
- Offers a tangible, shareable output

Considerations:

- Requires ethical care in crediting contributors
- Accessibility may be limited by cooking/growing resources
- Impact depends on thoughtful dissemination and follow-up
- Recipes should be simple, inclusive and culturally sensitive
- Publishing format and timing should align with audience needs

Who Am I?

Play and Game-Based Learning

Purpose

To spark conversation and reflection on biodiversity through a playful, accessible icebreaker. This method encourages participants to explore personal and cultural connections to nature, making biodiversity feel relatable and engaging. It is particularly useful for building rapport in workshops, community events or research settings.

Key Features

Participants:

- Ideal group size: 4–12
- Can be scaled up with multiple groups
- Suitable for all ages and backgrounds

Estimated Timeframe:

- Preparation: 30 minutes (basic) to a few hours (custom cards)
- Gameplay and discussion: 45 minutes total (flexible)

Budget Level:

- Low
- Requires only paper, pens, and optional printed cards or images

Materials Needed:

- Cards or paper with names/images of plants or animals
- Ribbon and Velcro, or Post-it notes, or other attachment method
- Optional: biodiversity fact cards for discussion
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)

Skills Required:

- Clear explanation of rules
- Inclusive facilitation and active listening
- Ability to guide discussion and manage group dynamics
- Sensitivity to emotional responses around biodiversity loss
- Adaptability and ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B UK case study to build connections between participants and biodiversity. Cards featured species familiar to the Chiltern Hills region. Researchers and participants played together, creating a shared space for learning and reflection.

How It Worked:

Each player received a card with a species name/image they could not see. Through yes/no questions, they guessed their identity. The game was followed by a facilitated discussion exploring cultural, ecological and personal associations with the species.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged through play, curiosity and storytelling. The method supported inclusive participation and could be adapted for different age groups or knowledge levels. Facilitators encouraged reflection and shared learning.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Fostered dialogue and rapport
- Prompted reflection on biodiversity and cultural meaning
- Created a foundation for deeper engagement
- Encouraged participants to take the game into other contexts
- Supported emotional connection to nature

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Simple, low-cost, and adaptable
- Encourages inclusive and playful engagement
- Can be tailored to local biodiversity or cultural themes
- Builds trust and curiosity
- Suitable for warm-ups or standalone activities

Considerations:

- Impact depends on quality of follow-up discussion
- Species must be guessable and relevant to participants
- Facilitators should be prepared for emotional responses
- Not designed for formal data collection, but useful for rapport-building, and potentially also for providing an opening insight into participants' knowledge, perceptions and feelings towards featured species
- Can be cascaded into other settings with simple instructions

PATHBREAK: Biodiversity JENGA®

Play and Game-Based Learning

Purpose

To raise awareness of biodiversity loss and ecosystem fragility through a hands-on, interactive game. This method uses a modified JENGA® tower and gameboard to simulate ecological dynamics, linking everyday actions and systemic pressures to species gain or loss. It encourages reflection, dialogue and collaborative learning.

Key Features

Participants:

- Ideal group size: 2–6 players
- Scalable with multiple towers for larger groups
- Suitable for all ages and knowledge levels

Estimated Timeframe:

- Gameplay: 5–15 minutes per round
- Discussion: 15–40 minutes
- Optional: multiple rounds with adapted rules

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include JENGA® set, colouring materials, printed [gameboard](#) and optional tokens or cards

Materials Needed:

- JENGA® tower with coloured ends (6 species categories)
- Printed gameboard (standard and blank versions)
- Six-sided die and player tokens
- Optional: species fact cards, discussion prompts, recording tools
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)

Skills Required:

- Clear facilitation and rule explanation
- Ecological framing (optional but beneficial)
- Sensitivity to group dynamics and emotional responses
- Adaptability to different contexts and audiences
- Ethical awareness

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in PLANET4B as an icebreaker and educational tool. Players moved around a gameboard responding to prompts (e.g. forest fire, pollution), removing or adding blocks to represent species loss or restoration. The game ended when the tower collapsed, symbolising ecosystem breakdown.

How It Worked:

Players rolled a dice, moved tokens, and followed board instructions. Each action corresponded to a species group, prompting removal or addition of blocks. Facilitators narrated scenarios and guided post-game discussion, linking gameplay to real-world biodiversity challenges.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged through play, storytelling, and reflection. The method supported inclusive participation and could be adapted for different learning levels. A blank board allowed groups to co-create rules based on local biodiversity issues.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Fostered ecological awareness and systems thinking
- Prompted reflection on human impacts and restoration
- Created space for dialogue and emotional engagement
- Encouraged cascading use in other settings
- Served as a gateway to deeper methods (e.g. storytelling, PATHBREAK – A Biodiversity-Food-Governance Game)

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Visually and physically engaging
- Accessible and adaptable across contexts
- Encourages collaborative learning and dialogue
- Can be tailored to local biodiversity themes
- Supports emotional and cognitive engagement

Considerations:

- Simplified model; ecological complexity must be discussed
- Requires preparation (colouring blocks, printing board)
- Impact depends on quality of post-game facilitation
- Trademark use must be acknowledged (JENGA®)
- Best used as part of a broader engagement strategy

PATHBREAK: A Biodiversity–Food–Governance Game

Play and Game–Based Learning

Purpose

To explore the complex relationships between biodiversity, food systems, and governance through collaborative role–play. PATHBREAK invites participants to step into diverse roles – farmers, policymakers, citizens – and navigate real–world dilemmas, trade–offs and decision–making processes. The game fosters critical thinking, empathy and systems awareness.

Key Features

Participants:

- Minimum: 7 players
- Maximum: 14 players (2 facilitators recommended for larger groups)
- Suitable for age 13+, including adults at university level and beyond, as well as mixed groups in participatory stakeholder workshops

Estimated Timeframe:

- Preparation: 2–3 hours (first–time facilitators)
- Setup: 30 minutes
- Gameplay: ~90 minutes
- Debrief: 30–60 minutes
- Total session: ~2.5–3 hours

Budget Level:

- Low
- Game is open access and free to download
- Costs may include printing, venue hire, refreshments and optional documentation

Materials Needed:

- Printed gameboard and role cards; Tokens for indicators
- Laptop with internet access; Projector or screen (recommended)
- Facilitator manual
- Spreadsheet for tracking decisions (included in the Web App)
- Post–game survey (included in the Web App)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data, also included in the Web App)
- Optional: camera or recorder (with consent)

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and inclusive communication
- Conflict management and intercultural sensitivity
- Ability to explain rules and guide gameplay
- Framing reflection and linking to real–world relevance
- Adaptability and ethical awareness
- Optional: experience in teaching or stakeholder engagement

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Piloted by PLANET4B international consortium members, students at the Martin Luther University Halle–Wittenberg, and the Urban Youth Learning Community in Germany, as well as with groups not part of the project. Participants explored biodiversity decision–making through role–play, experiencing systemic complexity and social dilemmas.

How It Worked:

Players assumed roles with varied social positions and interests. Through structured rounds, they made decisions, voted and negotiated. Facilitators guided gameplay and supported reflection, helping participants connect the experience to broader governance and biodiversity issues.

Engagement & Participation:

The method encouraged active participation, empathy, and critical dialogue. Facilitators supported inclusive engagement and adapted pacing to group dynamics.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Deepened understanding of biodiversity governance
- Surfaced tensions and trade–offs in decision–making
- Built empathy across roles and perspectives
- Strengthened group dialogue and collaboration
- Inspired real–world reflection and action

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Immersive and thought–provoking
- Supports systems thinking and social learning
- Adaptable across sectors and settings
- Encourages reflection and real–world relevance
- Open access and low–cost

Considerations:

- Requires skilled facilitation and preparation
- Emotional or complex themes may arise
- Impact depends on quality of debrief and framing
- Best used in a quiet, uninterrupted space
- The game does not result in a clear ‘winner’
- Follow–up reflection enhances learning

Systems Mapping

Behavioural and Choice Architecture

Purpose

To visually and collaboratively explore the relationships, behaviours, and structures that shape sustainability and biodiversity-related challenges. Systems mapping helps surface hidden dynamics, identify leverage points, and support inclusive planning and change-making across organisations, communities or teams.

Key Features

Participants:

- Ideal group size: 8–15
- Suitable for cross-functional teams, community groups or multi-stakeholder workshops

Estimated Timeframe:

- 1–1.5 hours (plus time for introductions and icebreakers if needed)
- Can be extended across multiple sessions

Budget Level:

- Low
- Main costs: staff time, facilitation, optional printing or digital platform access

Materials Needed:

- Large paper or whiteboard (or online tools like Miro/MURAL)
- Sticky notes in multiple colours
- Markers or pens
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Optional: stickers for prioritisation, camera/scanner for documentation
- Optional: refreshments or venue hire

Skills Required:

- Facilitation and inclusive communication
- Visual thinking and note synthesis
- Adaptability and ethical awareness
- Optional: systems thinking or stakeholder engagement experience

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in business and sustainability contexts to explore issues such as biodiversity volunteering, ethical procurement or workplace culture. The method helps identify barriers, enablers, and opportunities for change by mapping direct and indirect influences on a chosen issue.

How It Worked:

Participants defined a central issue and used an 'onion model' to map factors influencing it – starting with direct elements (e.g. policies, access) and expanding to indirect ones (e.g. culture, norms). Enablers and barriers were identified, prioritised and used to develop realistic change pathways.

Engagement & Participation:

The method encouraged open dialogue, reflection, and co-creation. Participants contributed insights from lived experience, helping surface emotional, relational and structural dynamics. Mapping was participatory and iterative, with space for diverse voices.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Clarified complex sustainability challenges
- Identified actionable priorities and leverage points
- Fostered shared understanding across roles and departments
- Supported inclusive planning and relational change
- Created a visual tool for ongoing dialogue and alignment

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and low-cost
- Supports deep reflection and systems thinking
- Adaptable to many contexts and issues
- Encourages inclusive participation and shared ownership
- Can be digitised and revisited over time

Considerations:

- Requires skilled facilitation to manage group dynamics
- Emotional or narrative insights may emerge; support needed
- Impact depends on follow-up and integration into planning
- Mapping should be positioned as a process, not a one-off
- Visual clarity and documentation are key for sharing outcomes

iNaturalist Biodiversity Observation

Behavioural and Choice Architecture

Purpose

To engage individuals and teams in observing, identifying, and sharing wildlife sightings through a citizen science platform. iNaturalist fosters connection to nature, supports ecological learning, and contributes to real-time biodiversity data. It is a flexible method that blends reflection, wellbeing, and environmental action.

Key Features

Participants:

- Anyone with access to a smartphone or camera
- Suitable for individuals, teams, or whole organisations
- Can be adapted for younger audiences using Seek (no account required)

Estimated Timeframe:

- Open-ended or time-bound (e.g. 1-day BioBlitz, month-long challenge)
- Flexible formats: lunchtime walks, weekend safaris, seasonal campaigns

Budget Level:

- Low
- Costs may include prizes, printed materials or borrowed devices

Materials Needed:

- Smartphone or camera
- iNaturalist or Seek app
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Optional: shared board or chat group, printed guides, prizes
- Optional: Miro board or feedback platform for reflection

Skills Required:

- Basic tech guidance (app use)
- Facilitation of reflection and storytelling
- Ability to link observations to broader biodiversity themes
- Adaptability and ethical awareness
- Optional: ecological framing or data interpretation

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

In PLANET4B, the method was tested among project partners as friendly photo-sharing challenge to promote workplace biodiversity engagement. It encouraged consortium members to observe nature in everyday settings – both during and outside of work – and contribute to ecological data.

How It Worked:

Participants used iNaturalist to record species. Monthly newsletters updated participants with the number of species observed so far, highlighting three recent observations. Themes included ‘purple plants’ and ‘spotted in Budapest’ following a consortium meeting there.

Engagement & Participation:

The method encouraged curiosity, creativity and collaboration. Participants reflected on their observations, shared stories, and connected across departments. It supported both individual mindfulness and collective ecological awareness.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Increased attentiveness to everyday nature
- Strengthened wellbeing and outdoor engagement
- Fostered team-building and cross-departmental dialogue
- Contributed to biodiversity data and reporting
- Inspired micro-actions and site-level improvements

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and low-cost
- Supports citizen science and ecological learning
- Encourages reflection and storytelling
- Adaptable across age groups and settings
- Can be embedded in wellbeing or sustainability programmes

Considerations:

- Requires basic tech support for app use
- Impact depends on follow-up and visibility of outcomes
- Data interpretation may need ecological framing
- Privacy and safety guidance should be provided
- Works best when linked to seasonal cycles

Nudging Experiments for Biodiversity Prioritisation

Behavioural and Choice Architecture

Purpose

To subtly influence behaviour by activating social norms and emotional responses that support biodiversity-conscious decision-making. Nudging experiments use low-cost, non-coercive interventions – such as messages, images, or default options – to steer choices without restricting freedom. This method is particularly suited to retail, policy and research contexts.

Key Features

Participants:

- General public (via surveys) or participants of real-world decision-making situations (e.g. shoppers; commuters; patients; policymakers)
- Suitable for quota-representative samples or diverse field settings

Estimated Timeframe:

- Survey design and piloting: several weeks
- Field experiment: 1–2 days per site
- Data analysis and reporting: variable depending on scope

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include survey platform access, printing materials, staff time and incentives

Materials Needed:

- Survey instruments (digital or paper)
- Nudging materials (e.g. trolley inserts, posters, messages)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Data collection tools (e.g. receipts, questionnaires)
- Optional: collaboration agreements with field sites (e.g. supermarkets)

Skills Required:

- Experimental design and data analysis
- Ethical oversight and informed consent procedures
- Stakeholder engagement and communication
- Optional: behavioural science or social psychology expertise

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in PLANET4B to test how nudges – framed around social norms and emotional appeal – could influence biodiversity-conscious shopping behaviour. A survey experiment assessed intended behaviours, while a field experiment in supermarkets tested real-world responses using trolley inserts and follow-up questionnaires.

How It Worked:

Participants were exposed to biodiversity-related messages (e.g. fact-based social norms, emotional appeals) and asked about their shopping intentions or observed in real settings. Data was collected via surveys and receipts. Analysis compared control and treatment groups to assess impact.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants engaged passively (via exposure to nudges) and actively (via surveys or interviews). The method allowed for broad reach, including groups less likely to participate in traditional research. Facilitators ensured ethical standards and clear communication. Young people accompanied the research throughout its different phases – learning about the method earlier and later contributing to its design, setup in the field, and finally serving as enumerators.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Identified effective nudges for biodiversity prioritisation
- Highlighted differences between intended and actual behaviour
- Informed institutional strategies for retail and policy settings
- Demonstrated potential for scalable, low-cost interventions
- Supported inclusive engagement across social groups, including by providing a learning opportunity for the involved young researchers

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Low-cost and scalable
- Suitable for both research and practice
- Can reach diverse and hard-to-reach populations
- Can generate actionable insights for institutional change
- Supports ethical, non-coercive behaviour change

Considerations:

- Ethical approval and informed consent are essential
- Impact depends on careful framing and context
- Deception must be avoided; transparency is key
- Best used with follow-up reflection or complementary methods

Photo Interview

Dialogue and Reflection

Purpose

To explore personal, cultural, and environmental perspectives through visual storytelling. Photo interviews invite participants to reflect on and share images that represent their experiences, values or beliefs. This method supports emotional expression, critical reflection, and deeper engagement with biodiversity and social change.

Key Features

Participants:

- Typically, 1:1 (interviewer and interviewee)
- Can be adapted for pairs, small groups, or focus groups
- Suitable for all ages; format should be tailored to context

Estimated Timeframe:

- Preparation: 1+ weeks for participants to take/select images
- Interview: 45–90 minutes
- Analysis and follow-up: variable depending on scope

Budget Level:

- Low to Medium
- Costs may include printing, travel, equipment and participant gifts

Materials Needed:

- Camera or smartphone (participant or provided)
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Recording tools (audio or notes)
- Optional: display materials (frames, boards, screens)
- Optional: exhibition or digital gallery platform

Skills Required:

- Active listening and open questioning
- Facilitation and emotional sensitivity
- Ethical awareness and consent management
- Analytical thinking and visual interpretation
- Basic photography and digital handling

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used in the PLANET4B Swiss case study to explore how religious beliefs influence farming practices and biodiversity attitudes. Farmers shared photos and video clips, which were later exhibited to highlight the connection between faith and ecological stewardship.

How It Worked:

Participants took or selected images on a theme (e.g. nature, farming, belief). Interviews were guided by open-ended questions, allowing participants to interpret and reflect on their photos. Visual and verbal data were analysed together and used in public exhibitions.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants led the conversation through their images. The method supported agency, emotional depth, and diverse forms of expression. It was adapted to suit different comfort levels, technical access, and cultural contexts.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Fostered personal reflection and ecological awareness
- Strengthened community dialogue and shared purpose
- Created visual outputs for exhibitions and advocacy
- Informed policy and institutional priorities
- Built lasting networks and collaborative potential

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and adaptable
- Supports emotional and visual expression
- Encourages participant agency and storytelling
- Can be used for exhibitions, reports, or campaigns
- Suitable for sensitive or complex topics

Considerations:

- Requires ethical care and informed consent
- Emotional responses may arise; support needed
- Impact depends on follow-up and visibility of outputs
- Works best when integrated into broader engagement strategy
- Visual analysis must respect participant meaning and context

Debriefing

Dialogue and Reflection

Purpose

To support reflection, emotional processing, and learning after a participatory or creative method. Debriefing helps participants make sense of their experience, share insights, and identify next steps. It strengthens personal and group impact and can also inform institutional learning or reporting.

Key Features

Participants:

- Ideal group size: 6–12
- Can be scaled up with multiple sessions or adapted for smaller groups
- Suitable for all ages; format should be tailored to context

Estimated Timeframe:

- 45 minutes to 2 hours
- Can be held immediately after the method or in a separate session (1–2 days to 2–3 weeks later)

Budget Level:

- Low
- Costs may include space hire, refreshments, printed materials, and facilitation time

Materials Needed:

- Paper, pens, mood cards, symbolic objects, drawing tools
- Institutionally approved ethical information and consent forms (if collecting data)
- Optional: audio recorder, camera (with consent)
- Optional: digital collaboration or voting platforms (e.g. [Padlet](#), [Mentimeter](#))

Skills Required:

- Group facilitation and inclusive communication
- Emotional sensitivity and trust-building
- Conflict resolution and time management
- Ethics and project coordination

Method in Practice

Context of Use:

Used across PLANET4B case studies and during multiple PLANET4B in-house consortium events to reflect on methods such as participatory theatre, drawing workshops, and biodiversity games. In the UK case study, for example, and during the final PLANET4B project event participants added reflections to a paper tree. In Hungary, debriefing with school students was co-facilitated by case leads and by external experts.

How It Worked:

Facilitators guided open-ended discussions using prompts, creative tools, and group activities. Participants reflected on emotions, insights and future actions. Debriefing was adapted to suit different ages, cultures and settings.

Engagement & Participation:

Participants shared thoughts through conversation, drawing, walking, or object-based reflection. The method supported emotional safety, inclusivity and diverse forms of expression. Co-facilitation and participant-led formats were encouraged.

Outcomes & Insights:

- Supported personal reflection and empowerment
- Strengthened group cohesion and trust
- Identified pathways for action and advocacy
- Informed programme design and institutional strategy
- Created outputs for exhibitions, reports or campaigns

Strengths & Considerations:

Strengths:

- Accessible and adaptable
- Enhances impact of other methods
- Supports emotional and cognitive processing
- Can be creative, informal, or structured
- Valuable for both participants and facilitators

Considerations:

- Requires sensitivity to group dynamics and emotional responses
- Format should match context and participant needs
- Ethical care and consent are essential
- Impact depends on quality of facilitation and follow-up
- Works best when integrated into broader engagement strategy

Understanding Transformative Potential: The Reflexivity–Situatedness Matrix (RSM)

1. Introducing the RSM

In PLANET4B, we explored not just what methods support biodiversity-related transformation, but how and why they work in different contexts. To help make sense of this, we developed a simple but powerful tool: the Reflexivity–Situatedness Matrix (RSM).

The RSM helps understand how interventions trigger change by focusing on two key dimensions:

- Reflexivity: How deeply a method engages people in conscious reflection and intentional change.
- Situatedness: How embedded a method is in a specific place, context or community.

Together, these dimensions offer a way to think about the transformative potential of different methods – whether they shift everyday choices, spark deep reflection, build change through local relationships, or facilitate thinking on values and worldviews that are deemed to be rather universal. The RSM also helps identify how methods can be combined to support change at individual (intra-personal), community (inter-personal) and institutional levels.

2. Why These Dimensions Matter

- Reflexivity helps distinguish between:
 - High: Deep, intentional reflection (e.g., storytelling, immersive workshops)
 - Low: Subtle nudges or default choices (e.g., framing, choice architecture)
- Situatedness helps distinguish between:
 - High: Locally grounded, context-specific interventions
 - Low: Interventions with abstract contexts and focusing on rather universal concepts

These distinctions help clarify how different methods work and what kinds of change they are likely to support.

3. How the RSM Supports Transformation

The RSM helps identify how methods contribute to transformation at different levels:

- Intrapersonal: Shifts in individual beliefs, values, and awareness
- Interpersonal: Changes in relationships, group dynamics and shared understanding
- Institutional: Influence on norms, policies and systems

It also supports reflection on:

- Power dynamics within partnerships
- Temporal dimension and selection of methods as an iterative learning process of aligning methods to actors, their contextual settings and their everyday lives
- Equity and inclusion, especially in how knowledge and decision-making are shared
- The role of different actors in shaping change

4. Interpreting Methods through the RSM

The methods in this catalogue vary not only in format and audience, but also in how they engage with transformation. The RSM offers a lens to interpret these differences.

Some methods invite deep reflection and personal transformation; others shift norms or behaviours through subtle cues. Some are rooted in specific places and communities, while others are designed to be widely applicable across contexts or support reflections on rather universal concepts and in abstract contexts.

By considering where each method sits on the reflexivity and situatedness spectrum, we can better understand its transformative potential. This perspective also helps facilitators and decision-makers combine methods in strategic ways – layering interventions to support change at multiple levels.

5. Using the RSM to Guide Transformative Practice

The RSM is a practical tool for:

- Strategic planning of interventions based on context, goals and available resources
- Combining methods across the matrix to deepen impact
- Matching interventions to the needs of different audiences and settings

It encourages thoughtful design and sequencing of interventions, helping practitioners build more inclusive, effective and context-sensitive approaches to biodiversity-related transformation.

You can read more about the RSM in this open access [scientific paper](#).

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PLANET4B

Find these and more engagement methods at
[Care-full-courses.com/care-full-resources](https://care-full-courses.com/care-full-resources)

Further Resources
[Care-full-courses.com](https://care-full-courses.com)

[PLANET4B.eu](https://planet4b.eu)

[PLANET4B Methodological Framework for Intersectionality Analysis](#)